

Perception of Unethical Behaviors among Nursing Educators, Students, and Staff in El Minia University

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Abstract: Unethical behaviors in nursing education are emergent problems that seriously disrupts the teaching-learning environment and often results in stressful student/faculty relationships. Nursing educator who demonstrate positive, respectful behaviors, encourage similar behaviors from their students. Conversely, educator who is aloof, disinterested, and demeaning may invoke their students' hostility. Nurse educators need to apply ethical behaviors in order to encourage a positive student-instructor relationship and to create a safe and nurturing environment. This study **aims** to identify the perception of unethical behaviors in nursing education among nursing educators, students and staff at El-Minia Faculty of Nursing. This study was **carried** out at faculty of nursing and Minia University Hospital. The study **sample** included a total number of 300: 200 students were enrolled in the four academic years (50 from each academic year), 50 Nursing educators, and 50 Nursing staff. Unethical behaviors in nursing education **questionnaire** was used for data collection. The study **revealed** that the most perceived academic unethical behaviors by the study sample were aggression, disregard for others and abuse of position. There were also a highly statistically significant difference between mean scores of academic unethical behaviors by the study sample, it is **concluded** that, the most perceived academic unethical behaviors by the study subjects were aggression, disregard for others and, abuse of position. Also, there was highly statistical significant difference between mean scores of academic unethical behaviors by the study sample. It was **recommended** to conduct a study to examine impact of student unethical behavior on the nursing profession and nursing educators.

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1. Introduction

Unethical behaviors in nursing education is an emergent problem that seriously disrupts the teaching-learning environment and often results stressful student/faculty relationships⁽²⁾. Nursing faculty who demonstrate positive, respectful behaviors, encourage similar behaviors from their students. Conversely, faculty who are aloof, disinterested, and demeaning may invoke their students' hostility.⁽³⁾ Also, Faculty members complain about the rise of unethical behavior in their students and students voice similar complaints about faculty.⁽⁴⁾

The increasing unethical behaviors and aggression of nursing students towards the professors is a concern for many reasons. Particularly because nursing students who exhibit aggressive behavior towards others in the academic setting will eventually care for vulnerable patients. In addition, it has been reported that unethical behavior on the part of students has made it more difficult to work as a nursing professor increases the anxiety level of nurse educators, driving some from the profession.⁽⁵⁾

Unethical behavior in both classroom and clinical settings is a concern for nurse educators and has the potential to greatly influence the quality of patient care.⁽⁶⁾ Moreover, Unethical practices among college students are concerning for any profession, but especially for nursing because these students will become health care providers after graduation.^(7,8)

Academic unethical behavior is defined as any speech or action that disrupts the harmony of the teaching-learning environment. It ranges from insulting remarks and verbal abuse to explosive, violent behavior. Academic unethical behavior is a serious problem and if left unchecked can it slowly erode a student's confidence and interfere with the teaching-learning environment in nursing education.⁽⁹⁾

Unethical behaviors in nursing education divided are into: Disruptive and threatening. The term "disruptive behavior" is defined as: repeated, continuous, and multiple student behaviors that hamper the ability of instructors to teach and students to learn⁽¹⁰⁾. It also refers to any verbal or physical conduct that

could potentially affect patient care. More overt disruptive behaviors include: verbal abuse, berating an employee in front of patients or employees, name calling, sarcasm, continual criticism, demeaning remarks, and rudeness (such as interruptions)⁽¹¹⁾. Disruptive behavior should be dealt with immediately since ignoring the behavior will likely cause it to increase. "Threatening behavior" includes: angry outbursts, physical threats and intimidation, bumping, stalking, or throwing objects. Physical assault, such as striking another, is rarer but does occur.⁽¹²⁾

Student disruptive behaviors are identified as: avoidance, disregards for others, and integrity compromised. *Avoidance* is defined as limiting engagement with course content, course materials, or course activities. Student *disregard for others* consists of behaviors that disrespect other students, faculty, nurses, or patients and discount the needs or desires of other people. The third identified factor under student disruptive behaviors is integrity compromised. *Integrity compromised* is composed of behaviors where the ethics of nursing are breached as Charting nursing care not performed, denial of an error made in patient care, Being unprepared for the clinical experience, demanding make-up exams, extensions, grade changes, or special favors, creating tension by dominating class discussion and using cell phones or pagers during class. **Student threatening** behavior are identified as: aggressive antagonism and uncongenial actions. *Aggressive antagonism* is defined as dominating others in a hostile fashion. *Uncongenial actions* consist of behaviors that unsympathetic or disagreeable and unbecoming of a nurse as Challenging faculty and nurse's knowledge or credibility and Taunting or showing disrespect to faculty, nurses, other students, and patients.⁽¹³⁾

Faculty disruptive behavior include: abuse of position and disregard for others. *Abuse of position* is defined as improper use of power in the faculty role. It includes "making rude gestures or behaviors toward others" and "making condescending remarks or put, Refusing or reluctant to answer questions. Being unavailable outside of class, Being unavailable

for practice in the skills laboratory, Ignoring disruptive student behavior, and Subjective grading. *Faculty disregard for others* consists of behaviors that disrespect other students, faculty, nurses, or patients and discount the needs or desires of other people. Faculty **threatening** behaviors such as making “cutting remarks,” “being rude and unkind,” and “being condescending.” Graduating students describe faculty as “being mean to students.”⁽¹⁴⁾

Nurse disruptive behaviors include: disrespect other students, faculty, nurses, or patients and discount the needs or desires of other people. Nurse **threatening** behaviors as “being rude,” “challenging faculty’s knowledge or ability to care for patients,” “neglecting patients,” and making comments that disrespect students and patients.⁽¹⁵⁾

Understanding student attitudes and perceptions about unethical behavior may provide insights that could form the foundation for strategies that may decrease the frequency of unethical student behaviors. **Hassel et.al (2005)**⁽¹⁶⁾ suggested that, The change in the nature of student attitudes and behavior is widespread in many academic settings and is serving as the impetus for strategic changes being made by faculty and administrators throughout the nation.

Studies in this area could improve the teaching-learning milieu and assist in the development of effective strategies for violence prevention and intervention. This is a timely and significant study at a time when the nursing profession is faced with a shortage of nursing faculty and practitioners. A greater understanding of the problems associated with unethical behavior in nursing education may help to recruit nurses into the profession as practitioners and as faculty into nursing education.

Also, Recognizing and understanding the students’ perception of uncivil behavior demonstrated by nursing faculty will assist nursing administrators to construct programs for faculty development to improve student-faculty relationships, to design faculty seminars on effective classroom management, and to decrease stress associated with student-faculty conflict. Understanding the impact of nursing faculty unethical behavior on nursing students and knowing how students respond to uncivil encounters will help faculty and administrators more fully comprehend the students’ perception of academic unethical behavior in order to provide resources and support associated with the impact of this behavior.⁽¹⁷⁾

Addressing unethical behavior in nursing education is imperative and more research is needed to understand both student and faculty perceptions of unethical behavior in nursing education **Lashly and de Meneses (2001)**⁽¹⁸⁾ described academic unethical behavior as an important concern in nursing education. For this phenomenon, this study was conducted to Identify unethical behaviors in nursing education that perceived by nursing educators, students and nursing staff.

2. Material and Methods:

Research Design

A descriptive- exploratory research design was used in this study.

Setting

This study was conducted at El-Minia Faculty Of Nursing And El-Minia University Hospital.

Subjects

The study subjects consists a total number of 300. They were divided into 200 students (50 students from each academic year) for the academic year 2010/2011, 50 faculty members, and 50 nursing staff.

Tool

Unethical behaviors in nursing education questionnaire that was developed by Beck 2009⁽¹⁾ is modified and adopted by researchers. This questionnaire is composed of *three* sections. The *first* section contains demographic questions. *Section* two includes 122 items. For disruptive (58 items) and threatening (64 items) behaviors for student, faculty, and nurse. Disruptive behaviors divided into four subscales namely Avoidance (6 items), Disregard for others (33 items), Integrity compromised (6 items), and Abuse of position (13 items). Also, threatening behaviors divided into two subscales namely Aggressive actions (58 items), and Uncongenial actions (6 items). A 4-point Likert scale from zero (never) to 3(always) was used to indicate participants perception of student, faculty, and nurse’s about unethical behaviors occurred in the classroom, laboratory, and clinical area. Finally, the *third* section which includes three multiple choice questions about to what extent the unethical behavior in nursing academic environment is a problem?, did students or faculty are more likely to engage in unethical behavior in nursing academic environment?, and which of the three learning environments are unethical behaviors the most prevalent, Traditional classroom , Skills laboratory, or Clinical unit. Scoring system for data collection was calculated by summing up the scores of each item. 30 minutes was given for the study to complete it.

Methods

The study was executed according to the following steps:

- Permission to conduct the study was obtained from all responsible authorities of Faculty of Nursing and university hospital after explanation of the purpose of the study, at El-Minia University.
- The Unethical behaviors questionnaire was modified and translated into Arabic after reviewing the related literature.
- Questionnaire was tested for its content validity and reliability by 5 experts in the related fields in faculty of nursing (nursing administration [2 experts]) and faculty of education (methods of teaching [3 experts]).
- A pilot study was carried out on a sample of 10 nursing faculty, 10 students from each academic year, and 10 staff nurses to ascertain the applicability of tool.
- The questionnaire was individually administered to each faculty, student, and nurse in the study setting. Data were collected nearly six month (from 1/10/2010 to 30/3/2011) period for the academic year 2010-2011.

Statistical analysis

- The data from the participants were entered and analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences software (SPSS) for windows (version 11)
- Descriptive statistic e.g. frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation were calculated.
- F-test was conducted to determine significant differences between the scores of the faculty and students groups.
- A P value of ≤ 0.05 was used to assess the significance of the results.

3. Results

Table (1) illustrates the distribution of the study subjects according to their general characteristics. It was noticed that, the mean age for faculty, students, and nurses were 28.38 ± 5.27 , 19.91 ± 96 , and 27.70 ± 9.34 respectively. Nearly two third (66%) of the sample were females. More than one half (54%) of the subjects were demonstrators. The years of experience for staff nurses the mean scores were 8.86 ± 10.19 .

Table (2) shows that, the study subjects did report that the highest perceived level with items of aggressive actions and disregard for others. In relation to aggressive actions item, it was founded that, the highest mean scores reported by the students, faculty, and nurses sample were 33.46 ± 11.56 , 32.90 ± 13.47 , and 27.68 ± 14.78 respectively. Moreover, regarding disregard for others item mean scores of students, faculty, and nurses were 19.67 ± 4.8 , 18.88 ± 4.29 , and 15.44 ± 6.49 respectively.

Table (3) demonstrates the mean scores of faculty unethical behaviors. It was noticed that, the highest mean scores were regarding abuse of position with students, faculty, and nurses were 29.05 ± 7.53 , 26.48 ± 10.68 and 21.62 ± 11.58 respectively. Furthermore, the highest mean scores regarding aggressive actions item with students, faculty, and nurses were 48.6 ± 11.89 , 45.32 ± 16.13 , and 37.46 ± 19.12 respectively.

It was clarified from table(4) that, the highest mean scores in nurse disruptive behaviors perceived by the study sample regarding Disregard for others with students, faculty, and nurses were 31.12 ± 1.14 , 30.24 ± 7.67 , and 24.80 ± 11.89 respectively. Also, in relation to nurse threatening behaviors, the highest mean scores were nearly equal in both students (14.66 ± 5.26) and faculty (14.38 ± 5.82) followed by 11.96 ± 6.57 for nurses'.

Table (5) shows Comparison of the mean scores of unethical behaviors among the study sample. It was observed that, there was a highly statistical significant difference regarding disregard for others, Integrity compromised, abuse of position, aggressive actions where $F = 14.86, 10.05, 14.27,$ and 14.27 respectively.

Table (1): socio- demographic characteristics of the study sample (n=300)

General Characteristic	Faculty (N=50)		Students (N=200)		Nurses (N=50)			
	Mean + S.D		Mean + S.D		Mean + S.D			
1- Age:	28.38+5.27		19.91+9.6		27.70+9.34			
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	Total	
							No	%
2- Sex :								
Male	6	12.0	81	40.5	15	30.0	102	34
Female	44	88.0	119	59.5	35	70.0	198	66
3- Academic year :								
First	-	-	50	25.0	-	-	-	-
Second	-	-	50	25.0	-	-	-	-
Third	-	-	50	25.0	-	-	-	-
Fourth	-	-	50	25.0	-	-	-	-
4-Academic qualification								
Demonstrator	27	54.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Assistance lecturer	12	24.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lecture	11	22.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
5- years of experience	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.86+ 10.19	

Table (2) Mean Scores of Student's Unethical Behavior by The Study subjects

Student unethical behavior	Study group n=300		
	Faculty N=50	Students N=200	Nurses N=50
	X + S.D	X + S.D	X + S.D
Disruptive behaviors			
Avoidance	14.38+ 4.38	14.18+ 3.9	12.30+ 5.62
Disregard for others	18.88 + 4.29	19.67+ 4.8	15.44 + 6.49
Integrity compromised	15.38+ 4.53	15.37+ 3.96	12.28 + 5.93
Threatening behaviors			
Aggressive actions	32.90+13.47	33.46+ 11.56	27.68 + 14.78
uncongenial actions	13.48 + 4.21	12.42 + 4.07	10.46 + 5.11

Table (3) Mean Scores Of Faculty Unethical Behaviors by The Study subjects

Faculty unethical behaviors	Study group n=300		
	Faculty N=50	Students N=200	Nurses N=50
	X + S.D	X + S.D	X + S.D
Disruptive behaviors			
Abuse of position	26.48+ 10.68	29.05 + 7.53	21.62+ 11.58
Disregard for others	22.16 + 7.33	20.83+ 6.02	17.96+ 8.98
Threatening behaviors			
Aggressive actions	45.32 + 16.13	48.6 + 11.89	37.46 + 19.12

Table (6) depicts that, there was a highly statistically significant difference between mean scores regarding disregard for others $P=0.001$, Integrity compromised, abuse of position, aggressive actions where $F = 14.86, 10.05, 14.27,$ and 14.27 respectively. Moreover high score for the faculty, student and nurse regarded aggregation $32.90 \pm 13.47, 33.46 \pm 11.56$ and 27.68 ± 14.78 respectively.

Table (7) shows the Percent distribution of the study subjects about their perception regarding questions for the most prevalent learning environment with unethical behaviors, does unethical behavior a problem, and which are most likely engaged in unethical behavior in academic environment. In relation to sample answers with question (a) which of the three learning environments are unethical behaviors the most prevalent? it was noted that more than half (53.7%) of the sample reported that unethical behaviors most prevalent in clinical unit.

Concerning question (b) to what extent unethical behavior in academic environment is a problem? it was observed that the study sample reported their highest percent (79 %) with the response serious problem.

Moreover, as regards question (c) to what extent students or faculty are more likely to engage in unethical behaviors in nursing academic environment? it was observed that the majority (45%) of study sample perceived students are more likely to engage in unethical behavior followed by (31.7 %) who reported that both students and faculty are equal to engage in unethical behavior within academic environment.

Table (4) Mean Scores of Nurse Unethical Behaviors by The Study subjects

Nurse unethical behaviors	Study group n=300		
	Faculty N=50	Students N=200	Nurses N=50
	X + S.D	X + S.D	X + S.D
Disruptive behaviors Disregard for others threatening behaviors Aggressive actions	30.24 + 7.67	31.12 + 1.14	24.80 + 11.89
	14.38 + 5.82	14.66 + 5.26	11.96+ 6.57

Table (5): Comparison of mean scores of Unethical Behaviors by the study subjects.

Unethical Behaviors	Faculty (N=50)	Students (N=200)	Nurses (N=50)	F Value	P Value
	X + S.D	X + S.D	X + S.D		
Avoidance	14.38+ 4.38	14.18 + 3.96	12.30 + 5.62	4.14	0.017
Disregard for others	18.88 + 4.29	19.67 + 4.58	15.44+ 6.49	14.86	.001
Integrity compromised	15.38+ 4.53	15.37+ 3.96	12.28+ 5.92	10.05	.001
Abuse of position	26.48+ 10.68	29.05+ 7.52	21.62+ 11.58	14.27	.001
Aggressive actions	32.90+ 13.47	33.46+ 11.56	27.68+ 14.78	14.27	.001
Uncongenial actions	13.48+ 4.21	12.42+ 4.07	10.46+ 5.11	6.57	.002

Table (6): relationship between age and unethical behaviors by the study subjects (n=300).

Unethical Behaviors	Age of Faculty (N=50)	Age of Students (N=200)	Age of Nurses (N=50)	F (P) value
	X + S.D	X + S.D	X + S.D	
<i>Disruptive Behaviors</i>				
Avoidance	14.38 + 4.38	14.18 + 3.91	12.30+ 5.62	4.14 (0.017)
Disregard for others	18.88+ 4.29	19.67+4.58	15.44+6.49	14.86 (0.001)
Integrity compromised	15.38+4.53	15.37+3.96	12.28+5.93	10.05(0.001)
Abuse of position	26.48+10.68	29.05+7.52	21.62+11.58	14.27(0.001)
<i>Threatening Behaviors</i>				
Aggressive actions	32.90+13.47	33.46+11.56	27.68+14.78	14.27(0.001)
Uncongenial actions	13.48+4.21	12.42+4.07	10.46+5.11	6.57(0.002)

Table (7) Percent distribution of the study subjects about questions regarding the prevalence, problem, and engagement of unethical behavior in academic environment.

a) which of the three learning environments are unethical behaviors the most prevalent?	No	%
1- Traditional classroom	125	41.7
2- Skills laboratory	14	4.7
3- Clinical unit	161	53.7
Total	300	100
b) to what extent unethical behavior in academic environment is a problem?		
1- no problem	1	.3
2- moderate problem	58	19.3
3- serious problem	237	79
4- don't know	4	1.3
Total	300	100
c) to what extent students or faculty are more likely to engage in unethical behaviors in nursing academic environment?		
1- faculty members are more likely	70	23.3
2- students are more likely	135	45
3- about equal	95	31.7
Total	300	100

4. Discussion

Academic unethical behavior disrupts student-faculty relationships, creates problematic learning environments, and increases stress levels among students and faculty. Student unethical behavior can include minor annoyances, classroom terrorism, where students interrupt class by talking and affect each other, intimidation expressed through threats to give poor teaching evaluations, and threat of violence⁽¹³⁾.

The aim of this study is to Identify the perception of unethical behaviors in nursing education by nursing educators, nursing students and nursing staff in El-Minia University. It was found that The **student** unethical behaviors reported included Acting bored or apathetic, Holding conversations that distract other students Sleeping in class Neglecting patients in the clinical area , Charting patient care not completed Neglecting patients in the clinical area , Charting patient care not completed. In addition.

Lashly and de Meneses (2001)⁽¹⁸⁾ did examine students' behaviors and found that 95% of respondents reported student behaviors of lateness, absence from class, inattention in class, rudeness such as talking in class, and cheating on assignments and tests. More than half of the respondents reported serious inappropriate student behavior and 43% noted an increase in the frequency of disruptive student behavior as compared to five years ago.⁽¹⁸⁾

The results of the current study showed that, highest perception of unethical behaviors related students was reported by nursing students. These findings are supported by **Clark and Springer (2007)**⁽¹⁹⁾ who stated that students were more likely than faculty to consider student behaviors unethical. Moreover, the study conducted by **Luparell (2003)**⁽²⁾ suggested that, students in the classroom setting are aware of the behavior of their peers

In addition, Findings indicated that **faculty** unethical behaviors included Making rude gestures or behaviors toward others, Being distant and cold toward others, Refusing or reluctant to answer questions, Being unavailable outside of class, Taunting or showing disrespect to patients, nurses, and students, Neglecting patients in the clinical area .

This finding is consistent with **Luparell (2003)**⁽²⁾ findings which stated that students hold a negative perception about faculty motivations. Furthermore, **Clark 2006**⁽²⁰⁾, **Savage and Favret (2006)**⁽¹⁷⁾ found that students reported unethical behaviors with faculty including demeaning and belittling students, treating students unfairly, disrespectful of students, rigid, defensive, not interested in whether a student learns. and pressuring students to conform to rigid requirements and standards.

Moreover, **nurse** unethical behaviors reported in this study included Refusing or reluctant to answer questions, Making rude gestures or behaviors toward others, Making statements about being disinterested in the working with students, Making harassing comments (racial, ethnic, gender) directed at patients, students, other nurses, Taunting or showing disrespect to patients, students.

These findings are in line with **Rowe et.al (2005)**⁽²¹⁾ and **Sandra (2009)**⁽²²⁾ who stated that nurses have become a significant source of verbal aggression, decreased continuity of care, poor patient outcomes, and increased cost to hospitals. Also, nurses were the most frequent source of verbal abuse to other nurses. The most frequent types of verbal abuse included "anger, judging and criticizing, and condescension" . in addition, **Luparell (2007)**⁽²³⁾, **Luparell, (2008)**⁽²⁴⁾, and **du Toit, (2003)**⁽²⁵⁾, stated that Negative behavior from other nurses has been reported to be more frequent and/or disturbing than behavior of physicians, patients, or family members.

The current study also revealed a highly statistically significant difference between mean scores of perception about academic unethical behaviors by the study sample. This finding is in line with the finding of **Hanson (2000)**⁽²⁶⁾ who pointed out that faculty and students hold differing perspectives of classroom unethical behaviors

There was also a statistically significant difference regarding age between mean scores of perception about academic unethical behaviors among the study subjects. This finding agrees with the findings of **Beck (2009)** .⁽¹⁾ who stated a statistically significant difference between the beginning and graduating students for The behaviors included in the Faculty Disregard for Others

More than half of the current study subjects had reported that unethical behaviors most prevalent in clinical unit. This results in agreement with the a study conducted by **Roberts (1996)** .⁽²⁷⁾ who found that Some baccalaureate nursing students engage in unethical professional behaviors specifically in the clinical area where 59% of nursing students reported taking hospital equipment home and 54% of them reported discussing patients in public places or with non-medical personnel. Also, This finding could be related to the fact that graduating students have spent more time on different clinical units

The majority of the current study subjects had reported that academic unethical behaviors consider a serious problem. This finding is supported by **Hall (2009)**⁽²⁸⁾ who mentioned that the majority (61%) of both faculty and students surveyed view unethical behaviors as a moderate or severe problem in nursing education.

The study results showed that the majority of study sample perceived students are more likely to engage in

unethical behavior. This finding is supported by **Luparell (2004)**⁽²⁹⁾ and **Beck (2009)**⁽¹⁾ who reported that students were more likely to engage in unethical behavior in the nursing academic environment.

There was no statistically significant difference regarding Relationship between gender and mean scores of perception about Unethical Behaviors of the study sample. This result contradicts to **Bohy (2003)** .⁽³⁰⁾ results. He found little difference between male and female responses within the survey items about unethical behavior in the nursing academic environment

Savage and Favret (2006) .⁽¹⁷⁾ found that students reported uncivil encounters with faculty including gender and racial bias and humiliation in front of other students. Consequences of student anger and discontent include disrupted student-faculty relationships, problematic learning environments, and increased stress levels among students and faculty

The study conducted by **Lashly and de Meneses (2001)**⁽¹⁸⁾ . revealed that Faculty in higher education have reported being threatened, verbally abused, and pushed by students and students have reported being treated unfairly, overly criticized, and threatened by faculty

Nowadays, after revolution of 25 January there were misunderstanding in relationship among faculty, students, and administrators in educational environment. So that the researcher noticed rising of unethical behaviors in classroom and clinical area. Also, Knowledge needs to be developed in the area of incivility in nursing. Nurse educators are in a unique position to influence the development of professional and ethical behaviors. The relationships built with students may have a strong impact on such development. According to **Lubarell (2003)**⁽²⁾ there are five principles for an ethical student-teacher relationship. These include respect, communication that promotes growth (versus fear), setting of boundaries, consistent behaviors, and personal values. In particular, it is important that faculty facilitate student understanding of the need for professional behavior to remain consistent with personal values. Of course, this logic assumes that a student's personal values are similar to nursing professional values.

Conclusion:

1. The most perceived academic unethical behaviors by the study subjects were aggression, disregard for others and , abuse of position
2. The most frequently academic unethical behaviors perceived related to the faculty reported by students
3. There was highly statistical significant difference between mean scores of academic unethical behaviors by the study sample.
4. There was statistical significant difference regarding age between mean scores of academic unethical behaviors by the study sample.
5. More than half of the sample reported that unethical behaviors most prevalent in clinical unit.
6. The majority of the study sample reported that academic unethical behaviors consider a serious problem.
7. the majority of study sample perceived students are more likely to engage in academic unethical behavior.

Recommendations

I- Recommendations for nurse educators and programs

1. Nursing leaders, students and, faculty need to conduct conferences for the discussion and awareness of unethical

behaviors in nursing education and to seek effective solution , prevention and intervention

2. Develop a guide line for ethical and unethical behavior in nursing education in class room, laboratory, and clinical setting.
3. Developing a professional behaviors policy as a guide for students' behaviors.

II- Recommendations for further research:

1. Repeats of this study with a larger and more comprehensive sample from similar institutions.
2. Study to examine The Impact of Student Development on Incivility
3. Study to examine impact of student unethical behavior on the nursing profession and nursing educators.

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